

Quality Circles : An Integrated approach of Development Through Employees' Participation

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1. Introduction

The genesis of Quality Circles goes years back when Japanese economy was dwindling by the heavy blows of Second World War in 1945. Therefore, USA initiated to help Japan to strengthen its economy and to restore common-satisfaction in the country. *General Douglas Mac Arthur*, the commander of the occupational forces in Japan, was deputed to apply some mechanism through which reliability of Japanese industrial produce can be increased to pour-in funds for common development.

Thus, *General Douglas* with the help of *Dr. Kaoru Ishikawa* has developed 'Quality Circles' in 1960s. The application of this method improved the quality of their produce and increased the effectiveness of various factors of production *viz.* men, machine and materials. Further, Japanese products became 'hit' in every market. In 1975, they have become the synonyms of success in a very short span of time. Later on, all countries of the world started to apply quality circles in their industrial set-ups to achieve growth and development.

2. Meaning

Of all the factors of production *i.e.*, 5M's *namely* men, materials, machines, money and methods. Man is the most dynamic and deciding factor in the present industrial scenario. By the advent of twins of 20th Century — globalization and liberalization, Materials, machines, money and methods are siphoned among the fellow countries.

But, the human element can not be siphoned so easily. And, the human brain is the greatest asset of the universe as well as the

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organisation. A simple arrangement or disarrangement of human brain may make or mar the total progress.

The basic philosophy of Quality Circles is "a breaking up big population of employees into small working group for improvement". This is an extension of Workers' Participation in Management Concept. When employees work together, an informal relationship begins to evolve by their mutual nearness. This informal relationship becomes stronger than the formal industrial relations with the passage of time. A smart manager can use this informal relationship to achieve super ordinate goals of the company. This is quick responding, effective and sure shot. Employees discuss organization, their dissatisfaction and other problems at work due to this informal relationship. This way, a number of solutions come-out of their discussion; no matter positive or negative.

The Quality Circles are the formal structure of this informal relationship where in employees are provided a base to discuss the problems, the organization and the growth. More specifically—"Quality Circle is a small group of a defined number of employees (it can vary from 5 to 12) doing similar type of activity who voluntarily meet together on regular basis to identify improvements in their respective work areas using proven techniques for analyzing and solving work related problems coming in the way of achieving and sustaining excellence leading to mutual upliftment of employees as well as the organisation. It is a way of capturing the creative and innovative power that lies within the work force."

3. Concept

If employees are talked about their views regarding the organisation, they feel a type of upliftment. Moreover, when they are said to point-out pitfalls in the system and they locate the pitfalls and suggest some pathy for these pitfalls, they feel really psychologically satisfied by their work. The application of Quality Circles gives birth two benefits.

And, it is a tested ideology that the quality of the work of employees improves automatically when their suffocation is released. It gives a self-motivation to the hidden inner capabilities of the

employees. A number of work area bottlenecks are solved by them their selves without any help and forwarding.

But, this ideology has another side, too. The management must be very clear, definite, adjusting and open minded to apply this concept. If employees are not justifiably treated, they may become irritative and rational in their working.

4. Organizational Hierarchy of Quality Circles

5. Objectives

Objectives are those aims that are formed to provide an organized solid base to a group of activities. The objectives of Quality Circles are –

1. **Self Development** by bringing out the hidden inner capabilities of employees. And, to nurture them transforming into skills.
2. **Conflict Management.** Quality Circles put an organized and effective two-way communication into operation. This omits intermediate quarrels and disturbances. Further, it reduces inter departmental conflicts automatically owing to common participation.
3. **Behavioral Change.** Regular meeting in Quality Circles gives a change in the behaviours of the employees. Employees, who previously are used to averse to difficult and new job, become optimistic and initiating while attempting new and difficult jobs.
4. **Team Culture.** It projects a team culture in the organisation. Workers become aware about the benefits of team spirit. The works that generally used to end in failures are now, last in successes.
5. **Healthy Organizational Climate.** With the application of self-development, team culture, behavioural change and the conflict management, a healthy Organisational climate is established, which, further, motivates the employees to work hard towards a common aim.

6. Process

This process is operated through the statistical problem solving methods like Histograms, Bar-diagrams, Control charts and Graphical representation.

7. Quality Circles & India

Quality circles were introduced first time in India in November, 1997 by Public Works Department of Maharashtra to solve the problems in the construction of roads and to lessen the accident rates. This was the starting phase of quality circles in India. Now, it is steadily becoming well-known in other Government Departments. The formation of quality circles has benefited these departments by giving—

- (a) Education to the employees about work;
- (b) Modification in their inner skills;
- (c) Team-spirit;
- (d) Improved work culture; and
- (e) Creativity to work.

8. Conclusion

Quality circles are not limited to manufacturing firms only. They are applicable for variety of organizations where there is scope for group based solution of work related problems. Quality circles are relevant for factories, schools, hospitals, universities, research institutes, banks and government undertakings.

